

Syntactic Variation in Conversational Seychelles Creole

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1. Introduction

A special focus in the study of young languages is on socially conditioned variation which signals progress in their development (Sebba, 1997: 240). Observing language in use reveals its dynamics and shows how the resource, described in grammar books as a fixed system, is actually exploited by its users, based on their real-life communicative needs in various socio-cultural circumstances. For Seychellois Creole (hereafter SC), one of the official languages of the Republic of Seychelles, alongside English and French, analysis of its stylistic variation in particular communicative situations is of primary importance for a number of reasons. First, this is a young language which took shape within the last 250 years and was officially acknowledged as the national language in 1981. Though the language in its own right, standardized in a number of grammars, dictionaries and systematizing language descriptions (Bollée, 1977; Corne, 1977; Choppy, 2013; Michaelis et al., 2013; Gillieaux, 2017), it is still at the initial stage of elaboration, adjusting to serve the needs of various important socio-cultural domains such as education, media, politics, art, etc. However, little is known about how SC varies in stylistically different communicative situations, for example in unplanned, spontaneous conversations. Furthermore, alongside the extensive body of linguistic research on SC which mainly focuses on its evolution, genetic relationship with other languages, and typology of creole continuum (Bickerton, 1986, 1989; Baker and Corne, 1982, 1986; Michaelis, 2008; Haspelmath and Michaelis, 2003, 2015; Adone, 2004 etc.), insufficient attention has been paid so far to the description of its sensitivity to the context, related to situational peculiarities of its use. The importance of contextual research was emphasized at the dawn of SC grammatic description by Chris Corne (1977: 222), the author of *Seychelles Creole Grammar*, who wrote that ‘fragmentary indications of social (etc.) variation in SC suggest a fruitful area for future study’.

Hence, this paper sets out to explore syntactic peculiarities of SC in an informal conversation – the key domain of everyday communicative interaction. The study focuses on spontaneous speech production and explores to what extent the regular syntactic principles of SC clause construction are observed in an unprepared conversational situation. To achieve the above goal, the paper pursues the following research questions: What are the constituents order variations in a spontaneous SC clause? To what extent does a spontaneous SC clause vary

with reference to its completeness? What are the semantic implications of the above syntactic variations?

Spontaneous speech in this study is represented by inputs in a recipe sharing situation. Choosing recipe telling for investigation of syntactic variation in SC is motivated by the cultural importance of food-related communication (Norrick, 2011) and its inherent conversational nature. Generically, recipe telling shares some of the essential features of conversation (Payne, 2015: 357). First, as both language production and processing are happening in real time, there is little or no possibility for revision and editing. Second, the language input in recipe discussions is unprepared and locally managed. Third, the participants of a recipe discussion share a certain amount of contextual knowledge, which enables them to spare their communicative energy and not to mention some elements which are viewed as already known. Thus, talking about a popular national dish elicits spontaneous speech which is reflective of current discourse trends within a particular community and proves to be insightful for the analysis of context-related language specificity.

2. Research Context

The research material for this study was obtained through interviews with six native speakers (three males and three females aged from 22 to 82) in July and August 2019. Respondents were approached with the task of sharing the recipe for chicken coconut curry, a traditional Seychelles dish which, according to many, is by far the country's most popular dish (Le Nautique, n.d.). The interviews were unprepared, carried out either in home or work-free office environment, with all speakers knowing and being on friendly terms with the interviewer (a native SC speaker). The interviews were recorded and the interview transcripts made up a corpus of 1764 lexemes.

The study of SC syntactic organization is an essential element of research into this language development. Explorations to date include the discussion of universals (general language phenomena) and substrata (specific languages under certain social and historical circumstances) influence on such development resulting in SC current status (Bickerton, 1986; Baker and Corne, 1986). The syntax of SC was extensively studied from the perspective of language typology and language contact. Thus, its valency patterns and constructions were scrutinized to argue their affinity with Eastern Bantu substrate languages (Michaelis, 2008), as well as to contribute to the typology of ditransitive constructions in creole languages (Haspelmath and Michaelis, 2003). A number of features of SC grammatical design were employed in the analysis of cross-linguistic variation, providing evidence of the change from synthetic to analytic patterns in the diachronic process of 'analyticization' (Haspelmath and Michaelis, 2015: 3). SC is engaged in typological discussions on syntactic status and etymology of certain cross-linguistic structures (Bickerton, 1989; Gilman, 1993; Adone, 2004;

Adone, Brück and Gabel, 2018; Kriegel, 1996). The typology of various SC syntactic constructs is represented in a number of relevant systematising studies (Corne, 1988; Gramatke, 2019; Adone et al., 2018). Syntactic structures of SC were also explored with reference to ethno-syntax. As demonstrated in Adone et al. (2018), describing various types and functions of Serial Verb Construction in SC, its structure and interpretation is related to the cultural logic – the way the events are conceptualized on a cultural level.

Syntactic peculiarities in language are explored in relation to the utterance information structure, namely various strategies for utterance focus (Givón, 1990; Chafe, 1970, 1976; Lambrecht, 1994; López, 2014; Spears, 1993). Reportedly, for SC, the noun group focus is organized by different types of cleft, understood as ‘a biclausal construction consisting of a focus clause and a background clause’ whereby ‘the focus clause consists of the focus (i.e. the focused noun phrase) and normally a highlighter, either a copula or a focus particle’ (Maurer and the APiCS Consortium, 2013). For example: *Mon papa sa ki ti fer sa lakaz* ‘It is indeed my father who constructed this/the house’; *Bann zonn ki danse sa tinge* ‘It is only the men who dance the tinge (a kind of traditional dance)’; *Se Pol (menm) ki 'n pran sa liv*. ‘It is Paul (himself) who has taken the book’ (Michaels and Rosalie, 2013).

Morphosyntactic patterns enabling the focus shift are extensively explored cross-linguistically (López, 2014:2) and, in particular, in English (Prince, 1997; Ziv, 1994; Birner and Ward, 2019) and French (Rigault, 1971; Barnes, 1985; Ashby, 1988; Blanche-Benveniste, 1989; Nagy and Blondeau, 1999; De Cat, 2007; Knutson, 2012) – the two languages which have impacted the development of SC, first, as ex-colonial languages and, currently, as the two adjacent official languages in Seychelles alongside SC. Notably, moving the topically significant noun group outside the clause boundaries is considered to be a distinct feature of conversational language variety with a number of discourse functions (Ochs, 1979; Quirk et al., 1985; Nagy and Blondeau, 1999).

With reference to the above, the syntactic description of SC to date presents a broad-ranging account of a number of its key parameters, including grammatical organization, valency patterns and the typology of syntactic structures. However, there is no systematic description of how the standard SC syntactic patterns vary stylistically, in particular in a spontaneous conversation. The current paper closes this empirical gap presenting a systematized description of syntactic irregularities in spontaneous SC clauses in terms of their constituents’ order and completeness.

3. Syntactic variation in a spontaneous SC clause

3.1 Technical terms

As the sentence definition normally includes reference to punctuation (capitalised first word and a full stop at the end) and thus refers to the written language (Börjars and Burridge, 2010: 304), the main unit of analysis in this paper is a clause, understood as a linguistic unit built around a lexical verb, containing all the elements required by the verb, and often some optional modifiers (ibid: 295). Clauses categorize as main or subordinate types within a sentence.

Present analysis of syntactic peculiarities of spontaneous oral production in SC focuses on such syntactic parameters as clause constituent order and completeness. The above analysis engages various conceptualizations of clause elements depending on the level of treatment. Thus, the notion of syntactic functions – subject, object, predicate, adverbial – is referred to when speaking about the clause structure as it is described in the grammar of SC. These notions encode morphosyntactic instantiations of conceptual bits of information (e.g. what the sentence is about or what is said about the entity in focus, etc.) communicated by the clause. Furthermore, the concept of syntactic arguments – nominal elements that are grammatically related to the verb in the clause (Payne, 2015: 170) – is used to analyse the position of noun phrases in this clause as subject or object. Also, semantic arguments – participants of the situation named by the verb and referred to as roles based on their function – AGENT (the doer of the action), THEME (the entity affected by the action), INSTRUMENT (the means used to accomplish the action), etc. – are engaged to talk about the referents of the described syntactic elements (Fillmore, 1976; Huber and the APiCS Consortium, 2013).

3.2 Variation in the clause constituent order

SC has a Subject-Verb-Object structure (Corne, 1977; Choppy, 2013, Haspelmath and Michaels, 2003), which means that in a clause the subject regularly precedes the verb, and the object follows it. For example:

- (1) (M22) *Si ou pe al kwi ou kari koko poul...* ‘If you are going to cook your chicken coconut curry...’

Example (1) has a regular direct word order, where the subject *ou* ‘you’ takes the position before the verb phrase *pe al kwi* ‘are going to cook’, and the noun phrase *ou kari koko poul* ‘your chicken coconut curry’, which is a direct object, is placed after the verb phrase. The above direct word order is the same for affirmative, negative, interrogative and exclamatory clauses

(Choppy, 2013: 52-23). However, the direct word ordering in a SC clause can be manipulated and reconfigured for certain communicative reasons, resulting in syntactically distinct structures which deviate in their pragmatic features from their neutral, unmarked counterparts.

Such word-order transformations in spontaneous SC will be considered further in 3.2.1-3.2.3.

3.2.1 Dislocation

One of the prominent features of spontaneous SC word order is what is known in syntactic theory as dislocation. Payne (2015: 273) defines dislocation as ‘...placing of a clause element outside the syntactic boundaries of the clause’.

As mentioned by (Givón, 1990: 268), dislocation involves breaking the clause constituent into two parts: a noun phrase and a co-referential element, which can be a pronoun or a noun phrase including a pronoun, placed separately at different ends of the clause. For example:

- (2) (F68) *Sa kari koko, nou pou manz li avek friyapen bwi, swa manyok, swa bannann, swa patat, nenport gro manze.* ‘**This coconut curry**, we will eat **it** with boiled breadfruit, or cassava, or banana, or sweet potato, any staple food.’
- (3) (F 49) *La ou pou pran ou bann zepis, zonnyon, ou pou met ou delwil sofe e ou pou rousi li byen tou ou bann zepis ansanm enkli en pti git disel.* ‘Now you will take your spices, onion, you will heat your oil and you will stir **it** well **all your spices** together plus a little bit of salt.’

In both (2) and (3), the reference to the THEME (something to be eaten in (2) and something which is being stir fried in (3)) is established twice: by the noun phrase (*sa kari koko* ‘this coconut curry’ in (2) and *tou ou bann zepis* ‘all your spices’ in (3)), and by the objective 3d person singular pronoun *li* ‘it’. Technically, the notional direct object expressed by the noun phrase is moved either left, to the beginning of the clause, as in (2), or right, to the end of the clause, as in (3), while its co-referential proxy object expressed by the pronoun takes the regular object position immediately after the verb. Examples (2) and (3) represent two types of dislocation: *left-dislocation* or *preposing* (Payne, 2015: 273) realized by advancing the clause element (example (2)), and *right-dislocation* or *postponing* (ibid: 273) achieved by postponing it (example (3)).

In both examples (2) and (3), the proxy object which holds the regular postverbal position is a pronoun. Spontaneous speech structures in SC reveal cases where the co-referential object is a noun phrase including a pronoun:

- (4) (F49) ...*ou dife, ou sipoze redwi son lafors.* ‘... your fire, you (are) suppose(d) to reduce **its strength**.’

In example (4), possessive pronoun *son* 'its' in the noun phrase *son lafors* 'its strength', which functions as a direct object to the verb *redwi* 'to reduce', establishes co-referential connection with the noun phrase *ou dife* 'your fire', placed in clause-initial position. Both noun phrases instantiate the same semantic entity the speaker is referring to – the THEME, the first phrase, naming the object of reality (the fire) and the second one specifying one of its aspects (its strength).

According to Payne (2015), in languages with fixed word order '...unusual orders of nominals with respect to the verb can be very powerful signals of marked pragmatic statuses' (Payne, 2015: 272). Such enhanced pragmatic statuses for left-dislocation include topicalization or bringing the subject into the focus of attention (Givón, 1990: 265). Right-dislocation is referred to as an 'afterthought' or 'repair device' (Lambrecht, 2001). As illustrated by examples (2-4), the above statements hold for spontaneous speech in SC, where dislocation serves a number of functional purposes: left-dislocation introduces the topic ((2) and (4)), while right dislocation clarifies it (3). By either advancing or postponing the clause element, both types of dislocation create additional emphasis on it and enable the speaker to give the described entity more prominence. Thus, putting the phrases *sa kari koko* 'this coconut curry' (2) or *ou dife* 'your fire' (3) at the beginning of the sentence, the speakers unambiguously announce the topic of their utterance, focusing the listeners' attention on what exactly they are going to describe. Right-dislocation in (3) illustrates the speaker's local management of the audience's attention: first they use the pronoun *li* 'it' to anaphorically refer to the entity which, though not mentioned before, is viewed as identifiable and recoverable from the shared situation of speaking or common knowledge about the object of conversation. However, following the listener's reaction, the speaker re-codes this entity with a full noun phrase *tou ou bann zepis* 'all your spices'. The use of left- and right-dislocation in spontaneous speech helps the speaker to cope with the time constraints of live production, presenting complex semantic constructs in relatively short and focused syntactic units.

3.2.2 Fronting

Another notable feature of spontaneous speech syntax in SC is fronting, defined by Langacker (1974: 638) as 'moving some constituent C to clause-initial position'. Example (5) illustrates one type of fronting, known as Y-movement (ibid: 639), when the nominal element which regularly follows the verb is put in preverbal position at the beginning of the clause:

(5) (M 89) *Tousala ou kraze...ou met la pare.* 'All this you crush, you put here ready.'

In example (5), the direct object *tousala* 'all this', which according to the regular unmarked word order in a SC clause should follow the verb (Choppy, 2013:55), is advanced to the initial position. Fronting and dislocation have certain syntactic distinctions: fronted constituents stay within the clause, with no proxy elements in their regular position, while dislocated constituents are put outside the clause boundaries and are co-represented by the copy elements

in their regular clause position. However, pragmatic implications of fronting are similar to those of left-dislocation (cf. 3.1.1; examples (2), (4)): additional emphasis is created and the fronted element gets more prominence. In spontaneous speech, fronting, alongside left-dislocation, is a useful grammatical device which facilitates the speaker in arranging the utterance in terms of its components' communicative value. It is a kind of shortcut to semantically prioritized items, whose visibility is especially important in the context of real-time production.

3.2.3 *Inversion*

As mentioned earlier, SC is a Subject-Verb-Object language (cf. 3.1), whereby the subject regularly precedes the verb. Yet, researched recipe-sharing data reveal instances of *inversion*: placing the verb or part of the verbal phrase in front of the subject. For example:

(6) (F 49) *Selman fodre sa dile koko i en ti pe...* 'However **must** this coconut milk **be a little...**'

The syntactic distinction of inversion from fronting and dislocation is in the fact that while the latter deals with the clause constituents which normally follow the verb, the former affects the verbal phrase and the position of the constituents which normally precede the verb. Pragmatically, inversion, similar to fronting and dislocation, makes an important contribution to the overall communicated meaning: it serves the function of intensification through creating an extra focus. Thus, in example (6) inverted word order draws attention to a certain cooking step which the speaker views as especially important.

3.3 Clause completeness

Alongside variations in the order of clause constituents described in 3.2, spontaneous speech in SC is characterized by variations in the clause structure at the expense of either its reduction or expansion. In other words, the spontaneous clause in SC can exhibit omissions or insertions of certain elements, which will be further analysed in 3.3.1-3.3.4.

3.3.1 *Ellipsis*

One type of omission in spontaneous speech in SC is ellipsis, understood as the deletion of some grammatical units which can be recovered from the immediate linguistic or situational context (Nelson and Greenbaum, 2016: 194). For example:

(7) (M22) *Ou rap ou lay, ou zenzanm, kari pile, kannel si ou pe al met <Øobject> ladan.* 'You grate your garlic, your ginger, curry leaves, cinnamon if you are going to put <Øobject> in.'

The verb *met-e* ‘put’ used in example (7) is missing its direct object. However, this omitted element can be restored contextually as anaphora of *kannel* ‘cinnamon’.

As revealed by the sampled material, different clause elements can be omitted by ellipsis in spontaneous speech in SC, which is illustrated in examples (8), (9) and (10), featuring, respectively, subject, verb, conjunction and preposition ellipses:

- (8) (F49) ...*alors nou pou annan nou dile koko, ki nou pou'n fini prepare, ki nou pou'n rap de koko, kinou pou'n pers li ek enn ti morso delo so, <Øsubject> donn li sa bon zi koko epe.* ‘...so we will have our coconut milk, that we would have finished preparing, that we would have grated two coconuts, that we would have wrung it with a little bit of hot water, <Øsubject> gives it that nice thick coconut juice.’
- (9) (F68) *Sa i son manze ki al avek sa, <Øsubject/Øverb> pa diri ki al avek <Øobject>.* ‘This is its food that goes with it, <Øsubject/Øverb> not rice that goes with <Øobject>.’
- (10) (F 49) *Pa bliye <Øconjunction> nou pe koz <Øpreposition> en kari koko poul lokal’.* Don’t forget <Øconjunction> we are talking <Øpreposition> a local chicken coconut curry.

Ellipsis is caused by economy of communicative energy in the situation of limited conversational turn. It does not affect communication of meaning, though it does have some semantic implications as information is rendered in a more condensed and amalgamated way.

3.3.2 Incomplete clauses

Incompleteness is another characteristic feature of spontaneous speech in SC. Incompleteness is different from ellipsis as elliptical structures can be restored from the linguistic and situational context without loss of meaning, while incomplete utterances cannot. The speaker just breaks up abandoning the current bit of information and switches to a new topic. For example:

- (11) (F68) [*La nou kari koko i fini bon*]¹ [*nou met ater*]² [*nou pran nou en bon<...>*]³– [*nou pa manz ek diri ha*].⁴ ‘[Now our coconut curry is already cooked]¹ [we put down]² [**we take ourselves a good** <...>]³– [we don’t eat with rice that]⁴.’

Example (11) consists of four homogeneous asyndetically coordinated clauses. Semantically, the first three clauses are consistent, enumerating the steps in cooking, while the fourth one switches to a different topic – the serving advice. The semantic switch is preceded by an incomplete clause 3, which is missing the head noun in the noun phrase instantiating the direct object. The clause finishes with the *en bon* ‘a good’, leaving it unclear what exactly the speaker was going to offer to take. Incompleteness in spontaneous speech is motivated by the informal nature of conversation and the speaker’s focus on the message rather than grammar rules.

3.3.3 Inserts

As well as cases of clause reduction at the expense of ellipsis or incompleteness, there are, in contrast, cases of clause expansion at the expense of insertions. Thus, spontaneous speech clauses may contain some elements which are loosely connected with the rest of the clause semantically and stand out syntactically. For example:

(12) (M22) *Pour bwi konmsi kari koko poul, bann poul ki'n bwi.* 'To boil **like** chicken coconut curry, chickens which have been boiled.'

(13) (M22) *Ou met ou safran, ou bann zafer, fer ganny sa zoli pti kouler zonn konmsi.* 'You add your saffron, your things, to give it that nice little yellow colour **like**.'

Inserts serve as pause fillers or markers of informality. Similar to incompleteness, inserts are motivated by the speech unpreparedness and concentration on the message development rather than grammatic accuracy.

3.3.4 Tautology and repetition

Another case of spontaneous clause expansion is semantic tautology or excessive lexical repetition:

(14) (M22) *Mwan mon pou montre ou manyer pour bwi en poul.* 'Me I will show you how to boil a chicken.'

(15) (F68) [...likou] *nou sod li, nou plim li. Ler nou fini plim li, nou koup koup li ptipti, nou met li dan nou marmit...* '[...neck], we parboil it, we pluck it. When we finished plucking it, we cut cut it in small bits, we put it in our pot...'

In example (14) reference to the doer of the action, who is also the speaker, is established by two adjacent first-person singular pronouns: object pronoun *mwan* 'me' and subject pronoun *mon* 'I'. The difference between inserts and semantic tautology lies in the fact that inserts represent additional referents, tautologic elements are co-referential and represent the same entity. Though grammatically excessive, semantic tautology can have a number of functions. In particular, it adds expression to the utterance and stresses the importance of the communicated message. Besides, repetition of the two first-person pronouns mentioned above is to indicate that the action is done by that particular doer in a certain way that is different from the way other people do it. Also, it serves as an emphasis on the doer, specifying that this particular person is the one doing it, not someone else and not just anybody. In the same vein, parallel constructions and repetition of the pronoun *nou* 'we' with every verb in example (15), though being redundant grammatically, creates dynamic rhythm and expression in the culinary instruction the speaker is giving. Moreover, repetition of the verb *koup* 'cut' emphasizes the action of cutting, foregrounding the smallness of the resulting

pieces. Both types of repetition are motivated by the speaker's desire to be as efficient and precise as possible in conveying the message fitting in the limited speaking turn.

The types of syntactic transformations in spontaneous SC clauses are summarized in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Syntactic transformations in spontaneous SC clauses

Conclusion

The communicative situation determines the use of a linguistic resource and 'the form a message takes is affected by the function of the message' (Payne, 2015:10). Following from this, the speaker modifies available conventional structures of language to make them suit the purpose of communication. In particular, in a spontaneous conversational situation, standard syntactic regulations are modified under the influence of the speaker's task to communicate the intended message within the limited time and without preparation. The resulting spontaneous stylistic variation in the utterance syntax is of a patterned nature. It is underpinned by the generic communicative features of conversation, such as brevity, spontaneity and shared context, and driven by the speaker's balancing the information in a message through foregrounding the most important elements, omitting the elements which are contextually recoverable or introducing extra, clarifying elements. The speaker's communicative creativity is facilitated by the linguistic flexibility as '...increasing the

prominence of objective content is one of the most important functions of lexical and grammatical systems' (Langacker, 1974: 661).

In SC, syntactic variation in spontaneous speech includes changing the order of clause constituents and changing the clause size. The order of the clause constituents is manipulated through left and right dislocation, fronting and inversion (see 3.2.1-3.2.3). The above syntactic strategies enable the shift of communicative focus and result in enhanced pragmatic status of certain utterance elements. The clause size in spontaneous oral production can be either reduced (through ellipsis or sudden break) or expanded (at the expense of lexical repetition, redundancy and insertions) (see 3.2.1-3.2.4). Syntactic strategies of clause-size manipulation create opportunities for emphasis and clarification.

Revealed availability of patterned, context-based syntactic irregularities in SC serves as a signal of language diversification and the development of various stylistic varieties to serve the needs of its users. This, in turn, is a sign of increased language maturity, supported by Sebba's (1997:122) characterization of pidgin-creole continuum dynamics, whereby as the language 'expands and takes on a wide range of culturally appropriate functions, the increase in stylistic range is as notable as the development of the grammar'. Based on this study, alongside the reported lexical and gestural means for specified reference (Brück, 2016) or cleft distribution of clauses (Michaels and Rosalie, 2013), to construct emphasis in spontaneous conversation, SC has developed a patterned resource of clause modification engaging constituent order and completeness.

Moreover, the identified repertoire of spontaneous syntactic transformations in SC relates to the menu of emphatic communicative strategies in language (Chafe, 1970, 1976; Givón, 1982, 1990), and in Creole languages in particular (Veenstra Besten 1994; Byrne and Winford, 1993; Maurer and the APiCS Consortium, 2013). The above overlap points to one of the problems of the development of Creole languages as, according to Sebba (1997: 240), 'the obvious model for them [Creole languages] to follow – perhaps the only one which they can follow – is the 'high' language already used in the community'. To better understand the nature and the extent of the substrate influence on SC, further research needs to be done to trace similarities and differences in spontaneous syntactic transformations in SC, and English and French which, apart from historical relatedness with SC, are currently the two national languages in Seychelles alongside SC. Also, the comparison of SC with other Creole languages for the patterns of spontaneous syntactic transformations will be useful to understand universal mechanisms of manipulating linguistic form for information expression in oral communication.

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